

Electric roads as an incentive-alignment strategy for European freight decarbonization

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Abstract

The European Union is unlikely to decarbonize road freight on time through its current policy mix. This article argues that the main barrier is misaligned incentives across freight operators, vehicle manufacturers, charging providers, grid operators and policymakers. Under current conditions, delay is often rational: battery-electric trucks remain expensive to buy, public charging is costly to use and risky to expand, grid connection queues are growing, and stronger pressure on fossil-fuel use can be politically regressive when affordable electric alternatives remain limited.

The case is presented for integrating electric road systems (ERS) on dense freight corridors into the European charging infrastructure mix, as a strategy to align incentives across the transport system towards accelerated decarbonisation. The economics of ERS investments and operations favour low pricing and rapid scaling of the infrastructure. Equitable access to low-cost public charging for vehicles in motion is expected to strengthen the incentives to adopt electric trucks, through reduced vehicle pricing, operational costs, payload penalties and charging downtime. Grid connectivity challenges would be made less severe, and vehicle manufacturers would see increased demand for both new and retrofitted electric trucks. Europe should therefore treat ERS not as a niche technology, but as a potential incentive-alignment strategy within the road-freight charging mix, and use the current policy cycle, including AFIR revision, to enable corridor-scale pilots, mechanisms to facilitate ERS investments, and suitable market frameworks.

Introduction

The European Union has committed to deep greenhouse gas emissions cuts (55% by 2030, 90% by 2040 and 100% by 2050¹). Progress in the road transport sector is decades behind schedule, especially for heavy-duty vehicles, even measured against the weaker sectoral target of 22% reduction by 2030² (all versus 1990). The current policy mix relies mainly on sales mandates for new vehicles, deployment of static charging infrastructure and, soon, stronger carbon pricing. Approximately 98% of new heavy-duty trucks sold in 2025 and 99.9% of the EU fleet had combustion engines, and it will be politically difficult to displace this durable fleet quickly. Future targets can only be met with ambitious and strengthened EU and national policy action today^{3,4}.

In the past decade, multiple strategies have been pursued in the EU policy space to achieve road transport decarbonization, including various strategies to reduce road transport demand, renewable combustion engine fuels, electrification, hybrid electric vehicles with supporting hydrogen fuel cells, and accelerated scrappage of older vehicles. Available evidence to date indicates that replacement of the vehicle fleet with battery electric vehicles is the strategy among these that has strongest potential to, within a relevant timeframe, combine cost competitiveness, sufficient scalability and sufficiently

deep GHG reduction impact for an eventual end of fossil fuel use in EU road transport⁵. Key challenges that reduce the decarbonization impact of electrification are late ramp-up in new BEV sales, especially for heavy-duty trucks, and slow vehicle fleet turnover, especially in markets dominated by second- or third-hand vehicles⁵.

Accelerating the transition to BEVs is far from trivial. While slow progress is often attributed to a technology or ambition gap, I argue that it is better understood as an incentive gap and that current EU policies already push the limits of what many stakeholders can accept. Today, delaying the transition is often the rational choice. Vehicle users face high upfront costs and costly public charging; charging-point operators and grid operators expand cautiously because profitability depends on utilization and connection risk; vehicle manufacturers resist zero-emission sales quotas; and policymakers face backlash because stronger measures to discourage fossil fuel use are regressive (they disproportionately affects those who are least able to change) when affordable electric alternatives remain out of reach. This article focuses on how incentive alignment across the freight electrification ecosystem can be improved, which addresses an identified gap in the transport electrification policy literature⁶.

How electric roads change incentives across actors

Electric road systems (ERS) are a family of technologies that allow vehicles to charge while in motion, via overhead catenary lines, conductive rails in the road surface or embedded inductive coils⁷. High technical readiness has been validated in several European projects. ERS deserves serious consideration as a way to realign incentives across the transport system. By allowing vehicles to charge while in motion on dense corridors, ERS can reduce dependence on large batteries, lower the cost and operational penalty of electrification, improve utilization of charging infrastructure, and establish a low anchor for public charging prices.

The central argument of this article is that the addition of ERS to the European charging mix could realign the incentives that drive the actions of vehicle operators, charging providers, grid operators, manufacturers and policymakers, for a self-reinforcing transport-energy system that accelerates towards fossil-free road freight. Figure 1 shows a flowchart for this causal logic.

Figure 1: Causal flow chart illustrating how the addition of electric road systems (ERS) to the mix of charging infrastructure options could align the incentives of multiple stakeholders to drive quicker uptake of electric vehicles, quicker expansion of charging infrastructure, and lower pricing of public

charging. If in-motion charging via ERS becomes available, policy to support conversions of used diesel vehicles to BEV would be a synergizing complement, to alleviate a shortage of used BEVs that is likely to hold back the transition in markets dominated by used vehicles⁵.

Vehicle user incentives

For vehicle users, the problem is straightforward. BEVs still cost markedly more upfront than comparable ICE models. In mid-2025, battery electric trucks were typically priced two to three times higher than diesel equivalents⁸, with batteries representing most of the cost premium. Truck operators are further impacted by reduced cargo capacity caused by heavy batteries and non-zero additional stop time for charging, both of which can translate to a need for more than one BEV, including driver, to perform the work of one ICEV. BEVs can still be financially attractive when operational savings outweigh the increase in vehicle cost, but they have mainly gained acceptance among users with access to private charging at low energy cost, using either local solar power or cheap off-peak grid power. Truck configurations used mostly in urban and regional distribution that allow nightly depot charging saw five times higher BEV sales share in Q1–Q2 2025 than configurations used predominantly in long-haul operations with away-from-base charging⁹.

Used-vehicle markets are particularly resistant to measures that would accelerate electrification. With trillions in locked-in car assets¹⁰, and an estimated hundreds of billions in used truck assets, the European market for used vehicles can hardly be incentivized to abandon mid-life ICEVs in favour of new BEVs. There is then a natural lag between new and used EV market shares and, until approximately 2040 for cars and 2050 for trucks, most available low-cost used vehicles will have combustion engines. Supply of used EVs could be increased if e-retrofits, i.e., ICEVs in which the powertrain has been replaced with an electric motor and battery, could be made cost competitive. The evidence base on industrial-scale truck retrofits remains limited and highly segment-specific. Existing studies suggest that retrofit can deliver environmental benefits in some use cases, but that business-model, regulatory and subsidy dependence remain major barriers to broad market uptake. One key technical challenge is that cost, weight and volume constraints on batteries mean post-conversion range and performance are typically inferior to both used ICEVs and new BEVs¹¹. Until this changes, e-retrofits are unlikely to scale beyond niche segments and low-mileage operations.

ERS strengthens the incentives for vehicle users to adopt electric vehicles. On dense corridors, in-motion charging can supply a large share of route energy while the vehicle is in use, allowing smaller battery packs without sacrificing range, flexibility or reliability. As explained below, ERS operators are expected to set a very low price for in-motion charging. Together, that means ERS-adapted vehicles have lower upfront vehicle cost, carry more cargo, and can have higher productivity, compared with other BEVs. These marginal advantages will decrease with battery technology advancements but will not disappear entirely. In many vehicle operating patterns, even current battery technologies are sufficient to offer the same advantages against ICEVs.

The impact of policies focused on new vehicle sales alone is slow, with the mean age of registered heavy-duty trucks in countries like Greece and Italy being over 20 years. To rapidly reduce fossil GHG emissions, the maximum impact potential is higher for measures that target the fleet in use⁵. One possible route is e-retrofit: conversion of existing combustion-engine vehicles to electric drivetrains, which simultaneously raises supply of used BEVs and decreases supply of ICEVs. Today, retrofit economics are often weak because cost, weight and volume constraints do not allow batteries that yield sufficient operating range¹¹. ERS could improve these economics by reducing the cost-optimal battery capacity in all trucks and by reducing the cost of then-critical public daytime charging (discussed below). As batteries and electric drivetrains improve, some retrofits may compare more favourably with older used BEVs than is often assumed, because the reused chassis can be paired with newer propulsion technology. ERS would not make all retrofits viable, nor eliminate the need for supportive policy and technical standardization, but it could expand the segments in which retrofit

becomes a credible decarbonization pathway for the existing fleet. Even in segments where subsidies remain necessary, a reduced transition cost could improve the emissions reduction achieved per euro of public support.

Vehicle manufacturer incentives

For vehicle manufacturers, these same conditions make it difficult to profitably meet zero-emission vehicle sales quotas, which are thus resisted. As long as ICEVs represent most vehicle sales, manufacturers are disincentivized to abandon refined legacy ICE platforms, even when these yield high BEV manufacturing costs. Vehicle manufacturers are uniquely positioned to reduce e-retrofit costs through facilitation of mechatronics (hardware and software) integration, but lack such incentives when supporting e-retrofits could make it more difficult to reach new-sale quotas^{10,11}.

ERS improves incentives for vehicle manufacturers to transition to BEV production by raising BEV demand, in particular in vehicle applications with high intensity use on and near major transport corridors. If corridor charging reduces the need for very large batteries, manufacturers can more easily offer BEVs at lower upfront cost, lower weight and fewer operational compromises. That increases the addressable market size and improves the prospects for rapid scaling of BEV production volumes.

Removing the battery as the strongest determinant of vehicle performance further reduces European vehicle manufacturers' (and their suppliers') exposure to foreign battery supply chains, which they do not control. Furthermore, if ERS materially relaxes the fundamental component cost, weight and space barriers that today rule out economic viability of e-retrofits in most segments, policymakers could feasibly strengthen the incentives for vehicle manufacturers to offer or support vehicle conversions, rather than leaving decarbonization of the active fleet as outside the scope of industrial strategy. Early scrappage policies would likely indirectly raise new vehicle sales and may be preferred by vehicle manufacturers due to a better fit with current business models, but the literature on this topic does not appear to support an argument that total fleet turnover could be sufficiently accelerated through scrappage incentives.

Charging infrastructure and grid operator incentives

For charging-point operators and grid operators, cautious expansion is also rational. As of January 2026, public high-power charging in the EU was priced about the same as fossil fuels per driven distance. There is effectively a trade-off today between battery cost (including lost cargo capacity) and charging cost (including lost productive time), which suggests in-vehicle battery capacities will keep increasing as battery prices and energy densities improve. Avoidance of public charging indicates a gap between pricing and willingness to pay, which I believe indicates another misalignment of incentives. The costs of both grid reinforcement and charging infrastructure scale approximately linearly with peak power output. Levelized cost for sold energy is then determined by utilization rate rather than scale. Price control and site selection therefore become the primary tools for CPOs to keep utilization high, while too rapid expansion risks asset cannibalization and reduced profitability. Charging at small business sites are likely to be associated with higher (potentially externalized) grid upgrade costs, as such sites are less likely to provide the 30–50 years of stable demand that grid operators typically expect for full pay-back of capital-intensive network upgrades. Furthermore, annual capacity for grid upgrades is limited, and scalable strategies are needed to reduce multi-year connection queues in regions that already cannot keep up with combined demand growth from charging, industry, residential heating, data centres and other uses.

ERS allows grid operators to focus their efforts on supplying power to connections along main transport corridors, approximately every 20 km. The exact placement of connection points is relatively flexible. ERS connections will mostly be established on land owned by the same entity (the road operator), will rarely compete with other land uses, and will have predictable demand for decades to come. The hypothetical pan-European ERS network in Figure 2 would require only

approximately 1,000 connections to the electrical grid and 10,000 new feeder substations along the roads. Substation density and grid connection capacity would be upgraded progressively as ERS utilization increases. For comparison, there are approximately 50,000 major logistics sites in the UK alone, not including dedicated truck parking locations¹².

The cost of installing ERS scales primarily with road distance (approximately €2 million per lane km¹³) and is relatively insensitive to use. This means the infrastructure can only ever be cost-competitive where it will be intensively used, and that a profit-driven ERS operator will aim to ramp up total revenue as quickly as possible, to recoup sunk costs. To achieve this, simulations indicate that a profit-maximizing ERS operator will anchor public charging prices around €0.25-0.30 per kWh (assuming €0.2 per kWh for electricity and grid fees), excluding VAT, or 20-50% below current public charging prices¹⁴. The electricity demand from ERS is temporally well aligned with electricity generation from solar power.

Figure 2: An illustrative scenario of how 18,000 km of ERS network (red) could enable cost-effective electrification of approximately 80% of European truck traffic, including 85% of long-haul road freight. Road segment width indicates forecast 2030 traffic volume by heavy trucks¹⁵, of which the blue share indicates traffic on routes on which 50-100% of the energy demand can be supplied from this ERS network. Light-blue regions are within 100 km distance of the ERS network and easily reachable even with small battery packs.

Socioeconomic impact

The argument for meeting the charging needs of a future electrified road freight system in part with ERS is also an economic one: redirecting part of the necessary societal investment in charging infrastructure towards ERS is likely to yield substantial net savings for the European economy.

By 2035, around one fifth of total EU road freight is expected to be electrified⁵, and on the current trajectory, the installed share of final charging infrastructure capacity will presumably be similar. Parallel investments in ERS will allow Europe to complete its charging infrastructure buildout earlier¹³. At an expected installation rate of one lane km per day, 30 teams across the EU working 200 days per year could install approximately 18,000 km of bidirectional ERS over six years.

An ERS network of such scope, exemplified in figure 2, translates to an investment of approximately €70 billion, with an approximate additional €70 billion for capital and maintenance costs over a 30-year infrastructure lifetime. A gross estimate is that such a network would enable electrification of approximately 80% of European truck traffic, including 85% of long-haul traffic (figure 2), and that ERS would supply approximately 70% of total energy used by the affected trucks. These quantitative estimates are based on synthetic European road freight transport flow data¹⁵ and assumptions that ERS delivers power at two to four times propulsion power and is used by all trucks operating on routes of which at least 25% of the route distance is on ERS. At 336 billion total EU truck km per year⁵ and 1 kWh per km energy consumption, this translates to a levelized infrastructure cost of around €0.02 per kWh. Overnight chargers and future fast-charging stations may reach levelized infrastructure costs of approximately €0.03-0.10 per kWh, while levelized public charger costs in 2025 were approximately 17-27 €c per kWh¹⁴.

Sufficient access to in-motion charging enables corridor users to reduce in-vehicle battery capacities by 50-70 percent^{13,16}. If the battery capacity of half the EU's six million trucks is reduced by 400 kWh¹³ at €75/kWh, twice over 30 years, this brings an additional €180 billion in societal savings.

The average annual cost of EU fossil fuel imports for heavy-duty trucks is around €50 billion, while burning of the same fuels generates at least another €50 billion annually in social costs⁵. European electricity is significantly cheaper and is rapidly decarbonizing. The cumulative savings from reduced fossil fuel use will depend on the timing of scope of ERS installation.

Although the exact ratio depends on what progress would have been made in the absence of ERS, the potential economic upside of corridor-scale ERS appears large relative to infrastructure cost. Prior research that assessed the marginal transport system impact of ERS found that the additional infrastructure acts as an insurance policy, to greatly reduce the number of scenarios under which emissions remain high, without risk of detrimental impact¹³.

Conclusions and policy recommendations

For policymakers currently wishing to accelerate road transport decarbonization, the core problem is political credibility and voter base support. Recent research suggests that support for transport climate policy depends strongly on perceived distributive fairness, expected effectiveness and trust in government¹⁷⁻¹⁹. When a large share of vehicle users do not yet see a feasible path away from ICEVs, this puts strong measures against fossil-fuel use out of reach, such as BEV sales mandates, used ICEV import bans, high fuel taxation, differentiated road tolls or zero-emission zones. That further jeopardizes the credibility of future decarbonization targets.

The addition of electric road systems (ERS) to the mix of charging solutions should make it more realistic for policymakers to reach set greenhouse gas emissions reduction targets by making a stronger policy mix both more politically accepted and more impactful. In other words, replacement of static charging with ERS as the backbone charging solution in suitable regions does not only reduce

emissions directly by supporting electrification; it can also reduce resistance to the wider policy package needed for a full phase-out of fossil fuel use in road transport. Maintaining baseline geographical coverage of public static charging will remain necessary, in particular for overnight use, but the installed capacity can be reduced in regions served by ERS.

If ERS is to play that role, policy action is urgently overcome the institutional barriers that at present prevent a market introduction²⁰. EU policymakers should do four things. First, the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR) is undergoing revision during 2026. The opportunity should be seized to recognize ERS as part of the core charging mix on corridors and in regions where traffic is sufficiently dense, by allowing ERS installations to count towards national charging infrastructure density targets.

Second, operators of national road networks that do not themselves invest in ERS should be mandated to provide mechanisms through which private investors can propose, plan, install, acquire power supply for, and operate ERS infrastructure. The current lack of established procedures and uncertainty around these basics is the primary remaining barrier to investment and industrial commitment in ERS. It is important that ERS is not excluded institutionally before it can be tested economically. The most viable investment model may differ by region, whether public delivery, concession, public-private partnership or another regulated operator model.

Third, on the densest freight corridors, ERS investments of sufficient scale have potential to offer strong commercial returns, because payload and operational efficiency advantages increase the willingness to pay¹⁴, and because high utilization can keep levelized infrastructure cost low even at user prices below those of competing charging alternatives. Still, financiers for first-of-a-kind capital-intensive infrastructure classes may require some form of public de-risking mechanism for initial investments to be bankable. To validate theoretical results, Europe should urgently fund an ERS pilot of logistically relevant scale on a core international freight corridor (e.g., motorways E30 or E5) or in a region with dense regional road freight (e.g., Poland or northern Italy¹⁵). A commercial pilot could be partially funded through the EU Innovation Fund, supported by innovation and regulatory flexibility measures introduced by the Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA), giving public bodies better tools to develop concessions, tender processes, operator requirements and fee structures^{21,22}. If expected financial performance is confirmed, further subsidies are likely not required for ERS expansion on Europe's main freight corridors.

Fourth, operators of ERS on major public roads should not be restricted to the same per-kWh revenue-collection model as operators of present public charging infrastructure. Regardless of the profitability of the investment, this model is due to market failures unlikely to yield socio-economically optimal outcomes¹³. For instance, partial recovery of the largely fixed infrastructure costs via road tolls imposed on all potential ERS users allow for no-regret investments, reduced marginal fees for charging, high ERS utilization, and near-optimal outcomes¹³. Full cost recovery via road tolls is not advised, as this reduces incentives to maintain a high quality of service and to further expand the geographic scope of the infrastructure.

European policymakers should act now to align incentives across the road transport system, so that zero-emission mobility becomes not only credible and achievable, but also cheaper for society, less dependent on fossil-fuel imports, and accessible to a much broader share of vehicle users.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the author used ChatGPT in order to assist with improving the organization and clarity of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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